

doi 10.5281/zenodo.7781170

Vol. 06 Issue 02 Feb - 2023

Manuscript ID: #0800

TIME MANAGEMENT STRATEGY AND ORGANIZATIONAL SURVIVAL OF BAKERIES IN OSOGBO, OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of time management strategy on organizational survival in Bakeries in Osogbo, Osun State, and Nigeria. The cross-sectional survey research design method was adopted for the study. The 183 employees of the Bakeries make up the study's population. The sample size is 126 employees selected from the total population. To gather the necessary data, the researcher used a structured questionnaire. The data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and descriptive statistics. Findings show that 44% of the change in organizational survival was brought about by the dimensions of time management practice. Prioritizing work task has positive effect on organizational survival ($\beta = 0.482, 0.000 < 0.05$). Goal-oriented plans has positive effect on organizational survival ($\beta = 0.318, 0.000 < 0.05$). The study concluded that time management practice has a positive effect on the organizational survival of Bakeries in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Goal-oriented plans, and prioritizing work task as variables of time management practice has a positive effect on organizational survival. The study recommended amongst others that for employees to succeed in the organization they should be made to understand the significance of goal-setting since it guides all work toward accomplishing broad objectives on schedule.

KEYWORDS

Time management strategy, goal-oriented plans, prioritizing work tasks, organizational survival

INTRODUCTION

Every manager requires time as a crucial resource to accomplish the aims and objectives of an organization. It is so fragile that it can never be recovered after being misused; it can only be spent. Every manager is trying to find better ways to manage their time. Time management is crucial to both, whether it's the management of an organization wanting to improve operations or a person searching for better ways to use their time. The successful management of time has been emphasized repeatedly throughout history and has been considered essential to success (Pugh & Nathwani, 2017; Nasrullah & Khan, 2015)

People sometimes have too many duties to complete but not enough time for the things they want to do, which highlights the importance of time management. Time management creates order, increases productivity, and makes one happier (Cross & Jiya, 2020). As a manager, you must manage time well to improve a variety of organizational performances. How well you manage time will have a good or negative impact on how well your company performs. Since they must do a lot of tasks in a short amount of time, managers in Nigeria today face one of their biggest challenges: effective time management. In an organization, effectiveness (doing the correct thing more often than efficiently) and efficiency (being able to complete a task or arrive at the intended outcome without losing time) are what determine performance (Cross & Jiya, 2020).

The advice to develop personal goals is frequently linked with time management techniques. These objectives are written down and can be organized into a project, an action plan, or a straightforward task list. Priorities, deadlines, and priority ratings can all be allocated to specific tasks or objectives. Investing time in time management entails figuring out what one desires to get out of his daily activities. Effective time management emphasizes effectiveness over efficiency by allocating time in a way that appropriate results can be obtained from tasks within a certain time frame (Cross & Jiya, 2020).

The secret to effective time management is preparing and then protecting the scheduled time, which frequently entails retraining your surroundings, especially other people's expectations (Cross & Jiya, 2020). One of any organization's most valuable resources in the corporate sector is time (Adebisi, 2013). This is virtual because every organizational activity that contributes to its strategic objectives has a time component. Its management is essential for the survival and prosperity of the organization because it is a significant asset.

Organizational success is influenced by increased operational effectiveness. The association between time management techniques and organizational success has been empirically shown in studies (Claessens et al., 2007; Miqdadi et al., 2014; Njagi & Malel, 2012; Nonis et al., 2011).

Every organization needs time to accomplish its goals and objectives. The organization is greatly threatened by the attempt to achieve the desired result. International Labour Organization (ILO) (2016) claims that managers now face significant difficulty with time management. Numerous issues and difficulties confront organizations, many of which centre on ineffective time management.

Despite the foregoing, there seem not to be as much empirical research on the connection between organizational survival in Bakeries and time management strategies. Prior research tended to focus on other sectors, including banking and education

The subsequent research inquiries were developed:

- i. How do goal-oriented plans affect an organization's ability to survive?

ii. How much does organizational longevity depend on how job assignments are prioritized?

Review of Concepts

Concept of time management practice

Time is a finite time of existence or occurrence of an action, process, or state. It is the amount of time required for a specific task to be completed. Initially, time in this context only referred to work-related or business activities, but over time, the phrase came to refer to both types of activities. Igbokwe-Ibeto&Egbon (2012) define this perspective of time as all characteristics of time that are relevant to effective management. However, they stated that it is unreasonable to approach work or business time in isolation from other times, such as leisure, break, a social, holiday, and other times, due to the mutual impact of one over the other. This is because how any of the aforementioned times are managed will have an impact on your time at work.

Pleasure time, break time, holidays, etc. are times set aside by an organization for its staff to relax and refuel their physical and mental stamina before moving on to the next phase of the goal to enhance staff performance (Osawe, 2017). By the adage "all work and no play makes Jack a dull lad," these times must be respected. According to Ojo and Olaniyan (2008), time is an inexhaustible and universal resource that cannot be substituted by people. They contend that time cannot be stored like raw materials, amassed like money, or turned on and off like a machine.

Whatever occurs, time moves forward at a predetermined rate. No matter what his position, everyone is given the same amount of time. Time is a precious resource that is finite, dynamic, and unrecoverable. Because there are only 24 hours in a day, every minute spent is irrecoverable, restricted, and dynamic (it is never static) (Osawe, 2017). Time is a unique resource that a business owner (manager/supervisor) cannot rent, acquire, or store. It's a necessity in life and it moves at the same pace for everyone.

Time management is the art of controlling and organizing how much time a person devotes to various tasks. The concept of "time management" refers to how an individual plan and prioritize the amount of time spent on different things. The act or practice of exerting conscious control over the amount of time spent on particular activities, especially to increase productivity or efficiency, is described by Lucchetti (2010) as managing one's time. When completing certain tasks, projects, and objectives, a range of skills, resources, and techniques can be employed to manage time (Osawe, 2017). Allen (2001) claims that this group of activities covers a broad range and entails the following: planning, budgeting, setting goals, delegating, analyzing time spent, monitoring, organizing, scheduling, and prioritizing. Allen (2001) described time management as the behaviour people adopt to utilize their time more effectively. It also refers to the rules and frameworks that people use to consciously choose the pursuits of their time (Osawe, 2017)

Time management is a talent that each person is different at and that takes work to master (Cross & Jiya, 2020). Another definition of time management is a form of self-management that emphasizes knowing what to do, how to do it better, when to do it, and when the appropriate time is for that specific task (Savino, 2016). It has also been connected to reduced anxiety and improved academic achievement in students (Jenaabadi, Nastiezaie, & Jalalzaei, 2016). Time management is defined as "behaviour" when goal-directed tasks are carried out to use time effectively (Aeon & Aguinis, 2017). The three main elements of good time management are long-term planning, short-term planning, and time attitudes. (Aeon & Aguinis, 2017). According to Osawe (2017), goal-oriented plans and prioritizing work task dimensions can be used as time management strategies:

Goal-Oriented Plans

According to Macan (1994), setting goals and priorities is necessary for good time management. The first comprises actions like prioritizing chores to attain one's goals and setting goals to achieve them. Because it is the target one needs to reach, the goal should be SMART, which stands for specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and time-bound. as this will help you know where you are headed or determine if you are heading on the right route. The people who set goals and plan the actions to achieve them are the goal achievers because they develop a crucial habit of staying focused and completing their significant goals (Rich, 2012).

Planning daily activities and following them helps people realize the power of their target-seeking minds since it entails setting the big and minor goals that help us get closer to our targets. Any successful person must recognize the value of goal planning since it helps organize all of one's efforts and ensures that overall objectives are met on schedule. Any individual should define goals and identify the essential steps to move toward them to manage time, as stated in Franko & Pioggia's (2006) critical study of a person's life. Each of the three types of goals—long-term (year), intermediate-term (month), and short-term—informs the one below it (week and days). These objectives have potential since they support staying on course, particularly when put into practice.

For better cooperation and coordination, it can be claimed that if one person from a commercial organization is in charge of managing the annual audit reports, the other employees from the financial department must focus on the other tasks. Management is impossible without planning. Managers must plan what to do at each point in time based on the value of the available time. An employee cannot coordinate his or her tasks within the restricted time provided without properly arranging what to do at each time (Osawe, 2017). Setting goals and objectives are essential to time management since, without them, no experience would have any direction (Osawe, 2017). For organizational planning to be implemented on schedule, proper planning is essential. Business organizations require their employees to follow their plan of work for them to be qualified to carry out their duties (Korschun et al., 2014). Every employee must adhere to and uphold the correct coordination of work activities to manage the internal culture of an organization. Planning and coordinating operations effectively helps the organization maintain adequate time management. The personnel of nonprofit and commercial organizations will effectively make personal growth at work through the timely coordination of activities.

Prioritizing Work Task

To prioritize is to collaborate with others to identify tasks that are more important than others, as well as to organize project roles and responsibilities and alter priorities as necessary (Osawe, 2017). Nevertheless, the secret to prioritization is figuring out what needs to be done first to achieve your objectives. Taylor (2012) presents parameters to take into account when prioritizing activities based on the Eisenhower 1950s. He established a method of time management for himself by classifying jobs into four groups: urgent and important, urgent but unimportant, important but not urgent, and important but not also urgent.

(i) Urgent and important: Depending on the nature of the job, these are items that a management or individual should do right away and give higher priority. For example, in the pickle jar hypothesis, these are viewed as enormous rocks.

(ii) Urgent and unimportant: These are tasks that the manager or person must complete but are not crucial. Therefore, individuals or managers should delegate to those who are skilled in the particular activity to deal with urgent and important issues.

(iii) Activities that are entered on the calendar are those that are important but not urgent. Take breakfast, lunch, and dinner as examples. They are significant, but whether they are carried out depends on the individual.

(iv) Non-urgent and trivial tasks that are completed by the manager or another employee of the company are time wasters. As a result, it is advised that these time-wasting activities be minimized or stopped altogether.

According to Rich (2012), setting priorities for tasks or activities promotes goal achievement since it is the most effective step for aligning the goals to accomplish them. Additionally, it enables one to recognize which matters more than others at a certain time and to behave appropriately. When managers or employees understand what their roles include and what is expected of them, they become more effective and can easily prioritize their tasks. Time management, according to Bevius & De Smet (2013), is not only a productivity issue that businesses cannot control; it has evolved into an organizational issue whose core causes are deeply ingrained in corporate cultures. Therefore, businesses should make sure that people have the resources and incentives they need to manage their time well. Additionally, as top management in organizations takes time management seriously, it has evolved into an institutional discipline. The management team is in charge of identifying priorities, ensuring that the actions related to those priorities are completed, and minimizing time spent on non-priorities to promote effective time management.

Organizational Survival

Effective organizational survival Competitive propensity is frequently cited as one of the key elements in successful organizational survival. The potential to energize and function as a catalyst for all other resources makes organizational survival aggravation propensity the most dynamic of all the components used to generate wealth, according to most experts (Farahmand, 2013). Thus, productivity is crucial to the national economy as a whole, the organization in question whether it is commercial or not, and the survival aggravation tendency of any status (Farahmand, 2013). The ability of an organization to withstand the influence of both internal and external environmental forces is a prerequisite for its longevity (Biriowu, & Ofurum, 2020). The survival of every firm is impacted by external environmental elements such as political, sociocultural, economic, and legal considerations, among others. According to Lee (2006), an organization's ability to thrive in a dynamic and competitive business environment depends on how well it can leverage its human and material resources and learn to adapt to its surroundings. In the same vein, Huber (2011) claimed that organizational leaders must remain extremely concerned with adapting to changing surroundings if they are to survive. This suggests that for any organization to be able to survive, its executives must be able to adapt and stay current on environmental issues affecting their business (Biriowu, & Ofurum, 2020). They can achieve this by continuously examining their surroundings.

Organizations have varied conceptions of what it means for an organization to survive. Organizations must accomplish a variety of tasks or goals and operate in a complex environment with erratic inputs. Organizations are social systems, and because different parties have interests in them, they are not autonomous entities. Regardless of the specific role it performs, an organization must have the ability to adapt, be productive, sustain itself, and expand if it is to survive (Kumar & Aithal, 2019). Any organization's success depends on its ability to survive. Organizations must implement strategy and justly engage people if they want to grow and sustain company results. To motivate people, the management of the company must establish the ideal working environment, which promotes job happiness, organizational dedication, and high performance.

Theoretical framework

The Pickle Jar Theory is the foundation of this investigation. The pickle jar hypothesis is a time management technique that will help you prioritize your tasks. You can use it practically to get the idea. Take an empty pickle jar and stuff it with rocks. You can see that pebbles might be placed in the voids between the rocks. After adding pebbles, the jar gets more concentrated, but there are still some empty places that can be filled with sand. After that, add water and close the lid. The pickle jar stands in for human existence. The rocks that take up the majority of the area stand in for life's larger obligations. This suggests that people should devote more time to achieving these objectives. The stones/pebbles represent leisure activities that take less time than significant objectives. Last but not least, a person's everyday responsibilities act as the sand between his or her interests and aspirations. Water is the diversionary force that draws attention away from the path to success in human existence.

Review of Empirical Studies

The effect of time management on academic performance was examined by Alyami, Abdulwahed, Azhar, Binsaddik, and Bafaraj (2021) among diagnostic radiology technology students at KAU. Cross-sectional survey research was used for this study. From September 2020 to February 2021, it was administered to King Abdul-Aziz University diagnostic radiology technology students. 152 students were targeted for this study, and 142 of them completed the questionnaire, yielding a response rate of 93.4 percent. 75 (52.8%) of the 142 participants were female, and 52 (36.6%) were from the 2018 group. The majority of the students i.e., 107 (75.4 percent) had GPAs between 4.5 - 5 in 2020. In contrast, 37.3 percent of respondents said they manage their time. Here, 36.7 percent of students with 4 to 4.5 GPA strongly agreed that their academic performance suffered as a result of poor preparation, whereas 69.2 per cent of students with 4.5 to 5 GPA strongly agreed that they met their deadline (p-value = 0.005). Approximately 71 (66.3%) students with a GPA between 4.5 and 5 agreed or strongly agreed to create a to-do list or calendar (p-value 0.047). The survey finds that students believed that preplanning their studies had improved their academic achievement. Less than half of the students, nevertheless, said they were good at managing their time.

Akintayo, Shadare, Ayantunji, and Olaniyan (2020) looked at how time management affected the Nigerian banking sector's business performance. A survey research methodology was used, and a stratified sample procedure was used to choose 477 respondents in total. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire, and analysis was done using descriptive inferential statistics with a 0.05 alpha level. The results showed that time management techniques significantly improve corporate performance. Additionally, based on time management practices, it was determined that male and female respondents' evaluations of business performance differ. It was suggested that the organization set stringent deadlines for completing particular tasks and enforce them with internal controls. The period for job performance and workforce compliance should also be given weight and be included in the format of the appraisal for promotion at work.

Effective time management's impact on Northern Nigeria Noodle Company Ltd.'s organizational performance was evaluated by Cross & Jiya (2020). For the study, a survey research design was used. Examining how time management affects workers' performance is the study's principal goal. According to the study's conclusions, good time management and organizational performance are positively correlated. According to the results, it is advised that, all other things being equal, improving effective time management would result in an improvement in the organization's performance and that, to build a time-conscious organization, the company itself must streamline its time management process.

Employees of basic hospitals in north Gondar had their time management techniques and related aspects evaluated by Chanie, Amsalu, and Ewunetie (2020). Between March and April 2018, a cross-sectional institutional study of primary hospital staff in north Gondar was carried out. Data was gathered using a pre-tested, standardized questionnaire. 422 employees were chosen using a straightforward random sample method. Time management practice-related characteristics were found using bivariate and multivariate logistic regression models. It was found that the primary hospital staff did not generally manage their time well. Planning, organizational policy, pay and benefits, performance reviews, and where employees lived were all elements that were strongly related to how they managed their time. Conclusion: To improve employees' time management techniques, managers and staff members must carry out interventions on key issues.

According to the research by Sarhaddi, Haji, Soleimanpour, and Ghalavand (2019), time management serves as a mediator in the relationships between role conflict and job burnout among teachers employed by Iran's Zahedan technical training institutes. 200 teachers were chosen at random and investigated in a correlational pattern for this descriptive correlational study. Role conflict, job burnout, and time management behaviour questionnaires were employed to gauge the research variables. AMOS 23 software and the statistical procedure known as Data analysis was done using "path analysis.". According to the study's findings, the factor of time management mediates the relationship between the two variables of role conflict and job burnout.. As a result, the following hypothesis are made:

H1: Goal-oriented plans have a significant relationship with organizational survival in bakeries.

H2: Prioritizing work tasks has a significant relationship with organizational survival in bakeries.

Methodology

The cross-sectional survey research design method was used in the investigation. The 183 employees of the Bakeries in Osogbo, Osun State make up the study's population.

Using the sample size calculation formula from Yamane (1968), the sample unit of staff that was taken was calculated.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

The sample size is 126 employees selected from the total population. To gather the necessary data, the researcher used a structured questionnaire built on a five-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, uncertain, strongly disagree, and disagree. The research tool's reliability and validity were verified. A total of 124 questionnaires were returned, and 122 of those were usable. Consequently, the response rate is 97%. Using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) software version (23), descriptive statistics, and multiple regression analysis were used to analyse the data and assess the hypotheses in this study. Regression is appropriate for outcome prediction and the strength of the relationship, which is why these two types of analysis were chosen.

Descriptive Analysis

In selected Bakeries in Osogbo, Osun State, the respondents were asked to rate their agreement with statements on the impact of goal-oriented plans on organizational survival. The responses were rated on a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (strongly disagree). The amount of satisfaction with the test variables is typically measured by a mean value greater than 3.00. When the

mean is greater than the cutoff value of 3.00, it is considered satisfactory; otherwise, it is considered unsatisfactory. The outcome is shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of Time Management Practice

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.174	1.805		-.096	.924
	Goal-oriented plans	.370	.086	.318	4.330	.000
	Prioritizing work task	.593	.090	.482	6.576	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational survival

Table 2 Analysis of Variance

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	203.618	2	101.809	47.595	.000 ^b
	Residual	254.546	119	2.139		
	Total	458.164	121			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational survival

b. Predictors: (Constant), Prioritizing work tasks, Goal-oriented plans

Table 3 Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.667 ^a	.444	.435	1.4625

a. Predictors: (Constant), Prioritizing work tasks, Goal-oriented plans

Table 1 showed that goal-oriented plans has positive effect on organizational survival ($\beta = 0.318$, $P < 0.05$). Test of H1 indicated that goal-oriented plans have a significant positive effect on organizational survival ($0.000 < 0.05$). The result is in agreement with Osawe's (2017) assertion that an employee cannot coordinate his or her tasks within the constrained time available without good planning on what to perform at each time. This demonstrated how setting daily goals and sticking to them help people realize the power of their target-seeking minds because they help them define the big goals and smaller goals that help them get there.

Table 1 showed that prioritizing work tasks has a positive effect on organizational survival ($\beta = 0.482$, $P < 0.05$). H2 test result indicated that prioritizing work tasks has a significant relationship with organizational survival ($0.000 < 0.05$). This result is in line with Osawe's (2017) finding that prioritising joint work on tasks helps to identify more and less important tasks and activities, as well as to organize project roles and responsibilities; when necessary, priorities are adjusted. This demonstrated that the secret to prioritization is figuring out what needs to be done to accomplish the desired goals.

The *F*-ratio in Table 2 showed that the dimensions of time management practice significantly predict organizational survival, $F = 47.595$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that the regression model fits the study well and is important for the investigation. Table 3 showed the extent to which the dimensions of time management practice accounted for the change in organizational survival as indicated by the Adjusted R Square value, which shows that 44% of the change in organizational survival was brought about by the dimensions of time management practice.

Conclusion

The study concluded that time management practice has a positive effect on the organizational survival of Bakeries in Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. Goal-oriented plans, and prioritizing work task as variables of time management practice has a positive effect on organizational survival. Planning ahead and then protecting that time are the keys to effective time management. To do this, managers frequently need to recondition their environments, especially other people's expectations.

Recommendations

Employees must be taught the value of goal-setting so they may direct all activities toward meeting overall targets on time if they are to succeed in the organization. Depending on the worth of the time available, the manager should plan what to do at any particular point in time.

REFERENCES

- Adebisi, J. F. (2013). Time management practices and their effect on business performance. *Canadian Social Science*, 9(1), 165-170.
- Aeon, B., & Aguinis, H. (2017). It's About Time: New perspectives and insights on time management. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 31, 309-330. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2016.0166>
- Akintayo, D. I. Shadare, O. A. Ayantunji, I. O. & Olaniyan, T. S. (2020). Time management and business performances in the banking industry in Nigeria. *Journal of Human Resources Management and Labor Studies*, 8(2), 1-11. URL: <https://doi.org/10.15640/jhrmls.v8n2a1>
- Allen, D (2001) *Getting things done: the art of stress-free productivity*, Viking: New York
- Alyami, A., Abdulwahed, A., Azhar, A., Binsaddik, A., & Bafaraj, S. M. (2021). Impact of time-management on the student's academic performance: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Creative Education*, 12, 471-485. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2021.123033>
- Biriowu, C.S. & Ofurum, U. A. (2020). Employee engagement and organizational survival. *World Journal of Innovative Research*, 9(5), 79-92. <https://doi.org/10.31871/WJIR.9.5.3>
- Bevius, F. & De Smet, A. (2013). 'Making time management the organisation's priority' *McKinsey Quarterly*, January.
- Chanie MG, Amsalu ET, & Ewunetie G.E. (2020). Assessment of time management practice and associated factors among primary hospital employees in North Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia. *PLoS ONE* 15(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0227989>
- Claessens, B. J., Van Eerde, W., Rutte, C. G. and Roe, R. A. (2007). A review of the time management literature. *Personnel review*, 36(2), 255-276.
- Cross O. D. & Jiya N. S. (2020). Effective time management on employee performance of Northern Nigeria Noodle Company Ltd. *International Journal of Research Science & Management* 7(1), 72-82. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3612089
- Farahmand, N. F. (2013). Organizational survival aggravation tendency as organizational undertaking. *Business Management Dynamics*, 2(10), 81-91
- Franko, M., & Pioggia, L. (2006). *Making the right moves: A practical guide to scientific management* (2nd Ed). North Carolina. Howard Hughes Medical Institute.
- Hisrich, P (2002) Effective time management for high performance in organizations, *Journal of Nigerian Institute of Management*, 44(3), 21-26
- Huber, G. P. (2011). *Organizations: Theory, design, future*. In S. Zedeck (Ed.), *APA handbook of industrial and organizational psychology* (p.V1). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Igbokwe-Ibeto, C. J. & Egbon U. (2012). Enhancing employee performance in Nigeria through Efficient Time Management Frameworks. *Asian Journals of Economics and Financial Review* 2(5):635-647
- Jenaabadi, H., Nastiezaie, N., & Jalalzaei, S. (2016). The effect of time management training on students' test anxiety. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 5, 12-22.
- Korschun, D., Bhattacharya, C.B. and Swain, S.D., (2014). Corporate social responsibility, customer orientation, and the job performance of frontline employees.' *Journal of Marketing*, 78(3), 20-37.
- Kumar, P. M., & Aithal, P. S. (2019). Importance of time as a resource in managing organizations. *Proceedings of National Conference on Recent Advances in*

- Technological Innovations in IT, Management, Education & Social Sciences, ISBN No: 978-81-941751-6-2, October 2019, 45-52. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3513000>
- Lee (2006). Management succession planning and corporate survival in Nigeria: A study of banks in Port Harcourt. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(27), 153-176.
- Lucchetti, S (2010) *The Principle of Relevance*, Bangkok: RT Publishing.
- Macan, T. H. (1994). Time management: Test of a process model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 79(3), 381
- Miqdadi, F. Z., Almomani, A., Masharqa, M. S. & Elmousel, N. (2014). The relationship between time management and the academic performance of students from the Petroleum Institute in Abu Dhabi, the UAE'. At *ASEE 2014 Zone I Conference*. April.
- Njagi, L. K., and Malel, J. (2012). Time management and job performance in selected parastatals in Kenya'. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 2(5), 19.
- Nonis, S. A., Fenner, G. H. and Sager, J. K. (2011). Revisiting the relationship between time management and job performance. *World Journal of Management*, 3(2), 153-171.
- Ojo L.B & Olaniyan, D. A (2008) Effective time management in an organization: A Panacea or Placebo, *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 24 (1), 127-133
- Osawe, C. O. (2017). Time management: an imperative factor to effective service delivery in the Nigeria Public Service. *International Journal of Development and Management Review*, 12(1), 152-167.
- Pugh, C. M., & Nathwani, J. N. (2017). Time management. In *Success in Academic Surgery* (. 187-199). Cham: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-43952-5_15
- Rich, D. (2012). *Maintain focus: Multitasking and Managing Time*. Retrieved 20/08/2014 From World Wide Web
<http://www.kcpa.org/writable/files/DrinonsLeadershipExpress/dle8article.pdf>
- Sarhaddi, M, Haji G. A, Soleimanpour, M, & Ghalavand, M. (2019). Mediating role of time management in the correlation between role conflict and job burnout among the teachers working at Zahedan technical training colleges, Iran. *JOHE*. 8(1), 43.
- Savino, D. M. (2016). Frederick Winslow Taylor and his lasting legacy of functional leadership competence. *Journal of Leadership, Accountability and Ethics*, 13(5), 70.
- Taylor, H. (2012). *Benefits of Time Management*. Retrieved Aug.06, 2014, from the World Wide Web: www.taylorintime.com/articles